

Prioritising Catchments for Nature Restoration in Scotland to Support Climate Change Adaptation.

A report for NatureScot

28th March 2025

Summary

Climate change is already impacting on Scotland's communities, businesses, infrastructure, natural capital and nature's ability to provide ecosystem services. Restoration or enhancement of ecosystems at a catchment scale offers a significant opportunity for climate adaptation that achieves a range of multiple benefits for people and nature. Given the pace of climate change, we need to act now to restore nature to help us adapt to climate change.

This report provides the results of a combined analysis using integrated spatial data sets, desk research, expert opinion and stakeholder survey and interviews to identify proposed priority catchments in Scotland where nature restoration can deliver multiple benefits, including climate adaptation outcomes.

The objective of the study is to provide information and evidence to NatureScot and those agencies, organisations and stakeholders involved in discussions and decision making on which catchments to prioritise for restoration.

This project brings together technical mapping analysis, desk research and the views of key stakeholders to produce a single list of catchments. This prioritised list is the combination of the spatial analysis and responses to the stakeholder survey and key informant interviews. It was built based on the locations of risks identified from the survey *and* that have a higher normalised score from the spatial analysis.

Key Messages:

We have identified 18 proposed catchments and 4 sub-catchments as priorities for nature restoration to achieve multiple benefits. Using a combination of spatial analyses, desk research, researcher perspectives and survey and key informant interviews, these catchments and sub-catchments are identified in Figure 1 and detailed in Table 1 below (no specific order of priority).

Figure 1. Proposed priority catchments for nature restoration (no order of priority). Green dots indicate locations identified in the survey where respondents provide information on existing projects. Blue dots indicate where they perceive risks.

Table 1: Proposed Priority Catchments using combined analysis

Catchment	Priority from one or both methods	Spatial assessment justification for benefits and identification of risks (<i>limitations in italics</i>) Additional information from report reviews in []	Identified as priority in	
			Survey	Interviews*
Tay 4991 km ²	Both	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large areas of degraded peat†. • Largest catchment, flood risk reduction (e.g. to Perth). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2,100 properties at risk, £7.4m annual average damage**. See Local Plan District LPD 08 Sources • Securing water abstraction. • At risk of future reduced water availability therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Impacts on nitrates in south-east of catchment. • Opportunities to reduce soil runoff. • Large areas of designated sites (CNPA). • Within the Climate Ready Tayside regional adaptation partnership area • [Tay Special Area for Conservation] 	Yes: Six risks identified by participants, plus one existing nature restoration projects. (Bioregion Tayside, Tay Rivers Trust)	No
Forth 1028 km ² and Allan Water 216 km ²	Both	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits for securing water abstraction (Forth). • Large areas of peat† • Flood risk reduction. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 430 properties at risk, £1.4m annual average damage**. See Local Plan District LPD 09 Sources. • Reduced erosion risk (upper catchments) • Reduced flooding. • At risk of future reduced water availability in upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Favourable conditions for vegetation recovery (long growing season). • Large proportion of owned land (Allan). • Some reduced soil runoff risk (more in Allan). • [FORTH2O Policy Innovation Partnership] 	Yes: Four risks identified in the survey and two nature restoration projects (Forth Rivers Trust) Multiple nature restoration projects under way / delivered	Yes: Network Rail

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<p>Tweed 3349 km²</p>	<p>Both</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some benefits for securing water abstraction. • Flood risk reduction (e.g. Peebles). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4,600 properties at risk, £10.5m annual average damage**. See Local Plan District LPD 13 Sources • Large areas of peat† • Reduced erosion risk (upper sub-catchments) • Reduced risk of flooding (upper west and southwest sub-catchments). • At risk of future reduced water availability especially in elevated upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Favourable conditions for vegetation recovery (long growing season). • Large proportion of owned land. • Potential to reduce nitrates impact (NVZ in east of catchment). • Peatland areas in upper sub-catchments. • Reduced erosion risk (upper catchments). • Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) sensitive area. • [Tweed Special Area of Conservation] 	<p>Yes: Two risks identified and two existing nature restoration projects</p>	
<p>Clyde 1939 km²</p>	<p>Both</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits for securing water abstraction. • High number of buildings in catchment. • Flood risk reduction (e.g. Glasgow). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9,600 properties at risk, £22m annual average damage**. See Local Plan District LPD 11 Sources • Large areas of peat, some bare / eroded†. • Reduced soil erosion risk (upper catchment). • Reduced soil runoff risk (upper catchment). • Favourable conditions for vegetation recovery (long growing season). • UWWTD sensitive area. • Within the Climate Ready Clyde regional adaptation partnership area and Metropolitan Glasgow Sustainable Drainage Partnership area • Within the Clyde Mission action area 	<p>Yes: Two risks identified and one existing nature restoration project. (Glasgow Clyde Valley green network)</p>	<p>Yes: NHS Scotland Assure</p>
<p>Dee (Grampian) 2084 km²</p>	<p>Both</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits for securing water abstraction. • Large areas of peat, some bare and degraded†. • Flood risk reduction (e.g. Ballater, Aboyne, Aberdeen). 	<p>Yes: One risk and one existing nature</p>	<p>Yes: Scottish Water</p>

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10,000 properties at risk, £13.5m annual average damage**. See Local Plan District LPD 06 Sources • Reduced soil erosion risk (upper catchment). • At risk of future reduced water availability especially in elevated upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Reduced soil runoff risk (upper catchment). • Large area of designated sites (CNPA). • UWWTD sensitive area. • Within the Cairngorms Regional Land Use Partnership area • [River Dee SAC and Fresh Water Pearl Mussels] 	restoration project identified in the Dee	
South Esk (Angus) 563 km ² Including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Glen Prosen • Glen Isla • Glen Clova 	Both	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large areas of peat, some bare and degraded†. • Reduced flood risk (e.g. Brechin). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 230 properties at risk, £0.81m annual average damage** See Local Plan District LPD 07 Sources • Reduced soil erosion risk (upper catchment). • At risk of future reduced water availability especially in elevated upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Potential to reduce nitrates impact (NVZ at lower half of catchment). • Reduced soil runoff risk. • Ease of access. • Some designated site areas (CNPA in upper catchment). • UWWTD sensitive area. • Within the Climate Ready Tayside regional adaptation partnership area • [Esk Special Area for Conservation] 	Yes: Two risks identified in South Esk. (survey)	
Don (Aberdeen shire) 1317km ²	Both	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced flood risk (e.g. Inverurie, Aberdeen). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3,100 properties at risk, £5.9m annual average damage** See Local Plan District LPD 06 Sources • Large areas of peat, some bare and degraded peat in upper catchment†. • Reduced soil erosion risk (upper catchment). • At risk of future reduced water availability especially in elevated upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Potential to reduce nitrates impact (NVZ in lower half of catchment). 	Yes: One risk identified and one nature based project	

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some benefits for securing water abstraction. • UWWTD sensitive area. • Ease of access. • Some designated site areas (CNPA in upper catchment). 		
Deveron (Moray) 1232km ²	Both	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced flood risk (e.g. Banff and coastal areas). • 360 properties at risk, £1.3m annual average damage** See Local Plan District LPD 06 Sources • Some benefits for securing water abstraction. • Reduced soil erosion risk (upper catchment). • Areas of peat, some bare and degraded in upper catchment†. • At risk of future reduced water availability especially in elevated upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Potential to reduce nitrates impact (NVZ in lower half of catchment). • Reduced soil runoff risk in some areas. • UWWTD sensitive area. • <i>Mostly rented land</i> 	Yes: Two risks identified	
Devon (Clackmananshire) 198km ²	Both	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits for securing water abstraction. • Reduced flood risk benefits (e.g. Hillfoots Villages: Tillicoultry, Menstrie, Dollar). Considered catchment prone to flash floods. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 890 properties at risk, £1.6m annual average damage (59% river, 41% surface) See PVA 09/04 • Areas of bare and degraded peat in elevated parts of catchment • Reduced soil erosion risk (elevated parts of catchment) • At risk of future reduced water availability therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Reduced soil runoff risk in some areas. • Favourable conditions for vegetation recovery (long growing season). • <i>Mostly rented land</i> 	Yes: Two risks identified and one existing nature restoration project	

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<p>Doon (Ayrshire) 322 km²</p>	<p>One (spatial)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Securing water abstraction. • Flood risk reduction. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 730 properties at risk, £1.6m annual average damage**. See Local Plan District LPD 12 Sources • Reduced soil erosion risk. • At risk of future reduced water availability in upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • <i>Mostly rented land</i> 	<p>No</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Ayr 584 km²</p>	<p>One (spatial)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eroded peatland in upper catchment† • Flood risk reduction. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5,900 properties at risk, £10m annual average damage (includes Irvine catchment)**. See Local Plan District LPD 12 Sources • Reduced erosion risk (upper catchments) • Reduced soil erosion risk • Designated sites (upper catchment) • Favourable conditions for vegetation recovery (long growing season). • Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) sensitive area. • <i>Mostly rented land</i> 	<p>No</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Spey 2947 km² including the Kingussie sub- catchment</p>	<p>One (spatial)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits for securing water abstraction (distilleries) [see MOVING Project]. • Downstream reduced flood risk benefits. • Reduced erosion risk • Flood risk reduction (e.g. Spey Bay). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 700 properties at risk, £1.8m annual average damage**. See Local Plan District LPD 05 Sources • Large areas of degraded peat†. • At risk of future reduced water availability especially in elevated upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow (biodiversity and distilleries). • Potential to reduce nitrates impact (NVZ at lowest level of catchment). • Large area of designated sites (CNPA). • Partly within the Highland Adapts regional adaptation partnership area • Within the Highlands and Cairngorms Regional Land Use Partnership areas 	<p>No</p>	<p>No</p>

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<p>Ugie 333 km²</p>	<p>One (spatial)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to reduce nitrates impact (NVZ). • Small amount of peatlands. • Ease of access. • UWWTD sensitive area. • Within the Climate Ready Aberdeenshire regional adaptation partnership area 	<p>No</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Findhorn 786 km²</p>	<p>One (spatial)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced flood risk. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 560 properties at risk, £2.4m annual average damage**. See Local Plan District LPD 05 Sources • Large areas of peat, some bare and degraded†. • Reduced soil erosion risk. • Reduced soil runoff risk • At risk of future reduced water availability especially in elevated upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Ease of access. • Few Designated sites 	<p>No</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>North Esk (Angus) (765 km²)</p>	<p>One (spatial assessment)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large areas of bare and degraded peat. • Reduced flood risk. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 170 properties at risk, £0.56m annual average damage**. See Local Plan District LPD 07 Sources • Reduced soil erosion risk. • At risk of future reduced water availability especially in elevated upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Potential to reduce nitrates impact (NVZ at lower half of catchment). • Reduced soil runoff risk • Some designated site areas (Cairngorms National Park in upper catchment). • UWWTD sensitive area. • Within the Climate Ready Tayside and Climate Ready Aberdeenshire regional adaptation partnership areas. 	<p>No</p>	<p>No</p>

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<p>Earn 867 km²</p>	<p>One (spatial assessment)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits for securing water abstraction. • Areas of peat in upper catchment, some bare and degraded†. • Reduced flood risk (e.g. Bridge of Earn). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 730 properties at risk, £2.8m annual average damage** See Local Plan District LPD 08 Sources • Reduced soil erosion risk (upper catchment). • At risk of future reduced water availability especially in elevated upper catchment therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Potential to reduce nitrates impact (NVZ in north-east of catchment). • Reduced soil runoff risk. • Some designated site areas (Loch Lomond & Trossachs NP in upper catchment). • Within the Climate Ready Tayside regional adaptation partnership area 	<p>No</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Leven (Fife) 422 km²</p>	<p>One (survey)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced flood risk benefits (e.g. Methil and Leven). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 180 properties at risk, £0.82m annual average damage (75% from river flooding) (see PVA 10/03). • At risk of future reduced water availability therefore need for water retention to reduce low river flow. • Small areas of peat† • Reduced soil runoff risk. • Favourable conditions for vegetation recovery (long growing season). • Potential to reduce nitrates impact (NVZ in part of catchment). • Reduced soil runoff risk in some areas. • UWWTD sensitive areas in part of catchment. • <i>Mostly rented land</i> 	<p>Yes: Five risks identified</p>	

Notes:

* The maps shown in this report and the Supplementary Material include point locations for existing climate risk and areas of proposed or active nature based solution projects identified through the survey. Catchments identified in key informant interviews related to climate risk or areas of proposed or active nature based solution projects were not represented as data points in the spatial maps as they were collated and shared with project partners after

the spatial maps were created by JHI. They include climate risks identified in the Clyde (NHS Scotland Assure), the Dee (Scottish Water) and the Forth (Network Rail). This emphasises that the published report serves as a foundation for further conversation with infrastructure providers as a next step.

** Flood Risk Management Strategy Local Plan District. Note: example figure provided are for river flooding and do not include surface water flooding. Some properties at risk examples from SEPA Potential Vulnerable Areas.

† See Table 2 in Supplementary Material for peatland areas per condition class in each proposed priority catchment.

There are other catchments and sub-catchments, along with locations that are identified as Potential Vulnerable Areas that would benefit from restoration that are not listed above. We later provide a few examples where restoration would have single benefits or locations at risk. The survey analysis also identified the Dighty Burn in the Dundee Coastal catchment, but this is not proposed as a priority. A list of catchments identified through stakeholder survey and interviews is provided in Table 3. Further analysis is required to determine if it could be a whole catchment priority.

Scope

While this list is based on the best available data and evidence, it should be noted that not all priority criteria were able to be integrated into the analysis due to availability, scalability or coverage of datasets, and responses to the survey, while wide-ranging, are not statistically representative of the entirety of Scotland. For example, all of the proposed priority areas in Table 1 are on the Scottish mainland. However, there are significant climate hazards facing island communities across Scotland, with many areas extremely vulnerable to climate change impacts. Risks were identified in Orkney and the Outer Hebrides through the stakeholder survey, but were not identified through the spatial analysis. Nature restoration that can deliver adaptation outcomes should also be explored further for island communities.

This report should be used to inform further prioritisation by NatureScot, agencies, and stakeholders in each catchment. It is also important to highlight that all catchments in Scotland will be impacted by climate change and require adaptation action in the coming years. This report highlights catchments where early action on nature restoration would deliver the greatest multiple benefits. NatureScot and other organisations will also need to identify how action will be supported in all other areas in the years to come, too.

Next steps

- NatureScot will discuss the proposed priority catchments with other Government agencies and Scottish Government to confirm which ones are priorities during summer 2025.
- NatureScot will engage with a wide range of stakeholders later in 2025 to ensure that the right priorities have been identified, and fill any gaps in 2026
- NatureScot will complete a gap analysis by the end of Q2 2025/ 26 and identify where new landscape scale restoration projects are needed, with a view to working with other agencies and partners to develop these during 2026.

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Introduction

The **purpose** of this report is to present the findings of an integrated spatial analyses and stakeholder engagement process developed to identify proposed priority catchments in Scotland where nature restoration can deliver multiple benefits. Primarily these restoration benefits are:

- | Climate change adaptation: | Additional benefits: |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Reduced flood risk• Reduced water scarcity risk• Improved water quality• Reduced risks to infrastructure• Restoring resilient ecosystems | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Benefits for biodiversity• Climate change mitigation• Improvement in wellbeing and opportunities for recreation• Nature Networks |

These benefits have been used as a guide to inform the selection and use of spatial data to enable the analysis to identify priority catchments for restoration. However, there are many benefits arising from the restoration of nature, not all of which have been included as criteria in this assessment (e.g. 'Improvement in wellbeing' which is hard to quantify, or due to lack of data). Instead, we refer to these additional benefits where possible and provide supporting information. Supplementary Material Table 1 in the contains the list of criteria used.

The primary **objectives** of the study are to provide information and evidence to NatureScot and those agencies, organisations, and stakeholders involved in discussions and decision making on which catchments to prioritise for restoration. This consideration is being conducted as part of NatureScot's work to prioritise landscape-scale restoration¹, requiring information to identify where investment is most likely to meet multiple objectives for land and water as set out in the third Scottish National Adaptation Plan (SNAP3): "Landscape scale solutions are implemented for sustainable and collaborative land use, including protecting and enhancing Scotland's soils."^{2 3}

The **aim** of the research was to develop an integrated approach to combine multiple spatial data sets and priority assessment criteria, coupled with stakeholder survey and interview approaches to identify priority catchments and sub-catchments in Scotland. The information presented is based on current best evidence discernible from the available data.

The **context** for the study is that climate change is already impacting Natural Capital and Nature's ability to provide ecosystem services. The combination of climate trends (Rivington and Jabloun 2022) and more variable climate extremes (Rivington et al 2022) and loss of ecosystem services, particularly the buffering of climate extremes by Nature, is leading to increased threats to people, infrastructure, businesses and ecosystems (CREW 2022, CREW 2024). Restoration or enhancement of ecosystems through Nature-Based Solutions offers the opportunity for reducing risk that achieves a range of multiple benefits.

Spatially targeting Nature-based solutions helps increase the probability of successful outcomes (Finch et al 2023) and delivers better value for public investment. The strategic landscape zonation

¹ NatureScot is leading on action 2.1 in the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy Delivery Plan, to review and prioritise landscape scale restoration across Scotland

² <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-national-adaptation-plan-2024-2029-2/pages/6/#:~:text=Objective%3A%20Landscape%20scale,enhancing%20Scotland%E2%80%99s%20soils.>

³ This work will also support SNAP 3 PS3 - Partnerships for water resource planning and rainwater drainage networks are active in **prioritised catchments** to support drought resilience, flood resilience and climate resilient places.

for restoration supports the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy and informs discussion on the nexus between biodiversity, water, agriculture and climate change ([Gimona and Castellazzi 2025](#)).

Inclusion of foresight: the analysis includes the use of indicators derived from climate projections to enable consideration of future conditions, particularly potential meteorological water availability. Whilst there remains uncertainty in terms of what the specifics of the future climate will be like in Scotland, there is growing certainty of the overall change in trends and increases in variability leading to greater extremes than we have previously experienced.⁴

Exclusions: Spatial analyses were conducted for the whole of Scotland, therefore all catchments, but recognising that landscape scale restoration is unlikely on certain landscapes (urban, high value arable crop land), these have been clipped out after completion of the WISE2 method analysis.

This study has not quantified the scale of effort required for restoration or likelihood of successful outcomes. This is best done at the scale of individual catchments. It does not include cost-benefits analysis of restoration or the costs of inaction (i.e. the risks embedded in current patterns of land use and its management (for productivity and yield) which assumes a largely stable and predictable climate versus the warming and more chaotic climate (within and across years) we are in and moving further into). We have included consideration of the practicalities of restoration (i.e. distance from roads), and areas of priority from key informant interviews also consider the most relevant areas for action.

Note: A Supplementary Material document is also provided, with additional maps of normalised scores for specific spatial data layers, maps of other spatial data that helps inform discussions on identifying priority catchments, analysis of climate related risk disclosures from infrastructure operators, and details of the survey and key informant interviews, including specific locations identified by stakeholders of climate risks to infrastructure assets, and existing priority locations for nature restoration.

Methods

This study has taken an integrated approach combining different methodologies, including:

- Consultation to develop key objectives of what restoration needs to achieve and how to identify priority catchments.
- Co-construction of prioritisation criteria and inclusion of expert knowledge perspectives.
- Identifying, sourcing and integrating spatial data.
- Developing a spatial analysis method.
- Designing and deploying a stakeholder survey and undertaking key informant interviews.
- Review of sustainability disclosure reporting (including climate risk reporting) from all relevant infrastructure organisations in Scotland.
- Combination of geospatial and stakeholder consultation results to produce a list of priority catchments.

⁴ <https://adaptation.scot/scotland-and-climate-change/climate-change-trends-and-projections/>

Establishing objectives and prioritisation criteria

The context and objectives for the study and the criteria for catchment prioritisation and subsequent methodological approaches for the research were defined through a series of meetings and correspondence between NatureScot and the research teams at James Hutton Institute and Verture.

Priority criteria were co-constructed and then selected based on their level of importance and utility (red, amber, green rating for low, medium and high importance, see Table 1 in Supplementary Material). This resulted in a list of criteria used to inform the identification of the geospatial analysis approach and required spatial data. However, not all 'green' level criteria could be included in the geospatial analyses due to either data availability, utility or practicalities of integration (data format, scale etc.). Hence the geospatial analyses represent some prioritisation criteria, but not all. Where data layers have not been included the project team have used their knowledge of these datasets to 'sense check' the results of the analysis.

Respondents to the stakeholder survey of more than 50 respondents were asked to identify specific locations for nature restoration for climate adaptation based on identified climate risks or planned/existing nature restoration efforts. A similar request was made of research colleagues at the James Hutton Institute, including those not on the project team. This was used as a 'safety net' to ensure that the spatial analysis methodological approach used did not omit any key catchments, and to provide additional information to inform discussions.

Geospatial analyses

A spatial normalisation method was developed to enable multiple data sets to be integrated at the same spatial resolution (50m) and apply an objective approach to enable equal levels of priority per input data set. The study has utilised the WISE2 approach to multiple data set integration and analysis ([WISE booklet v2 Nov 2013 reduced size.pdf](#)). The key features here are:

- Different spatial data sets are integrated and standardised to the same spatial granularity to enable analysis and mapping.
- A normalised scoring method is applied to all data sets to ensure an equal weighting to avoid some data layers dominating the process.
- Additional data sets not compatible with the WISE2 approach are used as a secondary level of analysis.

This approach enables a combination of both a systematic method and individual data layers assessment. Further details are provided in the Supplementary Material.

Note: A Supplementary Material document is also provided, with additional maps of normalised scores for specific spatial data layers, maps of other spatial data that helps inform discussions on identifying priority catchments, and details of the survey and key informant interviews.

The list of prioritisation criteria and spatial data sets used is provided in SM Table 1 in the Supplementary Material.

Stakeholder Survey

To supplement JHI's geospatial analysis, Verture conducted a qualitative survey of infrastructure providers and local authorities to ask them where they think nature restoration can best reduce risks to their assets and to communities. The survey also worked to understand locations of identified

climate risks, and what strategies are currently being used to reduce these risks. A list of respondents is provided in the supplementary material.

Verture conducted an online survey and key informant interviews to understand more about how climate risks have been assessed and asked for locations of these assessments. Climate risks were mapped as was the use of nature-based solutions across non-governmental agencies, local authorities, public bodies/agencies, landowners, and infrastructure asset owners including the NHS, SSEN, Network Rail, Transport Scotland and Scottish Water.

The survey was distributed widely using existing networks and contacts, such as the Adaptation Scotland [Public Sector Climate Adaptation Network](#) and Climate Ready Infrastructure Forum [Scotland](#), and through promotion via Verture and Adaptation Scotland social media channels, website and e-newsletters. There were 50 responses submitted via an online survey. A list of all respondents to the survey can be found in the Supplementary Material.

The survey data was analysed for frequency of response for certain questions (common forms of climate risk) and general themes. An iterative approach was used, in collaboration with the James Hutton Institute, which informed the selection of priority locations for data analysis.

Insights were recoded for each organisation type. Specific responses to the survey questions “*Has your organisation identified any priority locations for nature-based climate adaptation, and if so where?*” and “*Are you already progressing any nature-based climate adaptation projects? If so, where?*” were mapped across Scotland using GoogleMyMaps (see SM Figures 36 and 37).

[Additional information sources and analysis](#)

Verture also conducted interviews with six ‘key informants’; infrastructure providers including NHS Scotland Assure, Transport Scotland, Network Rail, SSEN Distribution, Scottish Water and Scottish Government (NHS assets) to gather information of their understanding of climate risk, their assets and their use of nature-based solutions to reduce the impact of these risks on their assets. These interviews were conducted online, and the line of questioning followed the format of the survey. Scottish Gas Networks, Scottish Power Energy Networks and Scottish Canals were all sent a request for interview, but discussions were unable to be scheduled within the time available to complete this report.

To supplement understanding, a register of sustainability disclosure reports was also developed to identify existing or proposed nature restoration work being used to restore and enhance ecosystems and their value in mitigating risk and achieving multiple benefits.

Combined, the methods provide a rich perspective on the understanding of climate risk and identify specific areas of activity where nature-based solutions are being actioned across Scotland. The research starts to establish a shared understanding of co-benefit. The research also highlights the challenges in using both Nature-based Solutions to reduce risks and Nature Restoration to restore and enhance ecosystems for adaptation.

Results

Proposed Priority Catchments identified by spatial analysis

The catchments identified as proposed priority for restoration are shown in Figure 1 with justifications along with information from the survey and interviews are provided in Table 1 (no order of priority). This is derived from the WISE2 method and use of the primary spatial data sets available (see SM Table 1 in Supplementary Material).

Figure 2 shows the normalised scores from the WISE2 method. To interpret the map, a score of 1 (yellow on the legend gradient) indicates that there is agreement on the level of priority for the range of data sets used as input. This integrated weighting map can be used to identify areas where prioritisation will always be considered important for achieving the multiple objectives of restoration, based on randomised stakeholder preferences for what might be considered important.

The map is therefore a representation of an objective approach based on the data rather than preference for any particular prioritisation criteria.

The aim of this approach is to provide stakeholders involved in identifying priority catchments for restoration with an unbiased objective map on which to base discussion and inclusion of additional knowledge and preferences for particular priorities.

Figure 2 includes locations of Nature-Based Solutions projects (green dots) and locations at risk from a range of threats (blue dots) identified in the survey and key informant interviews (see Supplementary Material for details).

To interpret Figure 2, those areas with the brightest yellow have a score of 1, meaning that they are score highest across the range of criteria and have a high priority for restoration, whilst darker yellow / brown consistently have low scores hence lower priority for restoration.

The spatial granularity is at 50m (standard rasterization across input data sets) hence areas of larger, homogeneous spatial extent will be more visible in the output. In terms of influence however, this is something that is regulated by the multiple random weightings, as there will be runs in which these features will be weighed both high and low. No one dataset or feature will dominate and areas will only score highly where the datasets align regardless of the weightings used, i.e., consensus is reached by the random virtual stakeholders and a consistently high score is achieved. This method seeks to avoid issues of understating the risks associated with maintaining existing land use systems, e.g. in areas such as high quality arable and horticultural lands, by excluded them on the basis that restoration is unlikely to be feasible. The assumption is made that restoration will not be made across the entire catchment, but that high-scoring sites within each catchment are where this restoration will take place. The detailed granularity can help to inform discussion on specific sub-catchments or areas within them.

Figure 2. Normalised restoration priority score. Green dots indicate locations of existing nature restoration projects identified in the survey, blue dots are locations identified as at risk from climate change. Spatial granularity is 50m.

Figure 2 covers the whole of Scotland and includes areas where restoration is not currently likely as they are either under arable or improved grass land use and may have high commercial and supply chain value, or are urban areas or where access is prohibitive. Figure 3 is a copy of Figure 2 but has had these areas removed (white on the map). Areas of peatland have also been removed as these have been considered in research projects elsewhere⁵ focusing on peatland (and see [Peatland restoration prioritisation framework \(WISE2\)](#)).

⁵ [Home | Land Use Transformations](#)

Figure 3. Normalised restoration priority score with areas where restoration is not currently feasible removed (i.e. arable, urban). Green dots indicate locations of existing nature restoration projects identified in the survey, Blue dots are locations identified as at risk from climate change. Spatial granularity is 50m.

Proposed Priority Catchments identified by researchers in JHI

The following have been identified as proposed priority catchments and sub-catchments for restoration based on *a priori* expert opinion and personal ranking (1 = low, 10 = high, James Hutton Institute research staff) before the spatial analysis. This list was used as a cross-reference check with the spatial analysis and to add details of specific sub-catchments in the event these were not identified.

Note: This is a separate exercise to the stakeholder survey, the priority catchments identified in that process can be found in the section below:

Table 2: Proposed priority catchments identified through consultation with James Hutton Institute researchers.

Catchment (ranking 1 = low, 10 = high)	Sub-catchments	Justification (summarised from Hutton staff information)
South Esk (9)	Glen Prosen, Isla and Clova	EELG* catchment; flood risk (Brechin); stakeholder interest in restoration; large % of land use change potential. CREW has been in consultation with ENRA CSA Mat Williams and other colleagues in Scottish Government on the need to focus on the issue of soil erosion/bare ground in the South Esk.
Findhorn (8)		Extensive areas of degraded peatland.
Forth (8)	Allan Water Almond	Lot of existing activity including ForthERA/Forth2O/MOT4R/Hydro Nation Scholar research activity.
Spey (8)	Kingussie	Multiple industries: significant degradation, heavy reliance on biodiversity and water quality. Kingussie SEPA PVA with lots of flooding/sedimentation issues. Spey Partnership looking to restore this sub-catchment. more manageable scale than the whole Spey.
Nith (7)		Flooding, significant soil erosion risk.
Tyne (7)		WFD 2022 status; notable flooding areas; stakeholder (farmer) interest in restoration.
Almond (5)		Scottish Water priority catchment; high resolution monitoring by ForthERA & University of Stirling.
Eden (4)	Motray	Ongoing research and development of Decision Support Tool (monitoring opportunity). Solid track record of ongoing research, strong community involvement in restoration initiatives through the River Eden Sustainability Partnership, seedcorn pilot project funded by Nature Scot.
Cessnock, Mein, Abbey Mill, Greens Burn, Burnside Burn, Vinny Water (4)		SEPA intensive monitoring catchments

* EELG: Environment and Economy Leaders Group

Additional issues raised relevant to all proposed priority catchments include:

- Hydromorphological alterations are one of the key reasons why Scottish catchments are failing to attain good status (Water Framework Directive) in addition to diffuse pollution, sewage management and control of invasive species. These alterations have the potential to

exacerbate vulnerability to climate threats if they are not specifically designed as part of mitigation and adaptation efforts.

- Other restoration efforts (not detailed in the survey results) include:
 - Beltie Burn, Mar Lodge and Logie Burn re-meandering projects.
- Surface flooding in urban areas is highlighted as an increasing issue.

Proposed Priority Catchments identified by stakeholder survey

Many parts of Scotland are at risk to climate change, particularly the impacts of flooding, which was the most cited climate risk, followed by combined climatic effects, warming water temperatures, coastal erosion and prolonged periods of heat or cold. Key findings from the survey were:

- 88% of survey respondents have identified locations that are vulnerable to the impacts of climate change.
- With 92% of those already exploring the potential for nature restoration to reduce the identified climate risks.
- 85% of survey respondents said they were already progressing with nature-based climate adaptation projects.
- 65% of those who weren't already progressing with projects said they were interested in collaborating to deliver nature-based climate adaptation, with 34 email addresses being supplied in response.
- 56% of survey respondents thought that their organisation would be able to contribute towards the cost of nature restoration in their priority locations.

The types of locations identified at risk from climate change include rivers, a variety of urban locations, coastal regions and upland areas. Because locations identified in the survey considered risk at varied scales; from specific sites and specific assets through to neighbourhoods, urban areas more generally through to specific waterways and wider catchment level, its challenging to use this information pinpoint specific locations. Instead, they provide a view of prioritised areas of risk and start to build a shared geospatial understanding of areas of activity in using nature-based solutions to reduce the impact of these risks. This has been combined with the spatial analysis from JHI.

Table 3. Catchments identified as being at risk from climate change in the stakeholder survey

Catchment	Number of risks identified and mapped
Tay	6
Leven (Fife)	5
Allan Water	2
Devon	3
Forth River	4
Clyde	2
Tweed	2
South Esk	2
Deveron	2
Eden	2

Generally, locations towards the east of the country are where most climate risk has been recorded and attempts to reduce this risk through nature restoration highlighted by survey respondents. This aligns to some prioritisation from the key informant interviews particularly of water source challenges in Eastern regions exacerbated by shifts in population from West to East as well as lower rainfall. The maps (SM Figures 36 and 37) show respondent's indications of activities and risks create the impression that there isn't much effort in the West and regions like Glasgow⁶, but this is more likely due to the limited response rate from those regions. Further work is required to assess these risks.

From the survey, the majority of locations that have progressed nature-based projects are in the central belt and the East of the country. In the River Tweed catchment, there are multiple nature-based solutions being developed. Common types of nature restoration that were identified include natural flood management, woodland creation, sustainable urban drainage systems (SuDS) and peatland restoration.

The data collected from local authorities, public bodies/agencies and NGOs prioritised areas for nature restoration in city regions, neighbourhoods and "communities". They focus on areas of high population density but acknowledge the role of the wider catchment in relation to climate risks. This list doesn't highlight all the nature-based solutions done or in progress in urban areas.

Table 4. Catchments identified with nature restoration projects being progressed in the stakeholder survey.

Catchment	Sub-catchments	Number of nature restoration projects
Tweed		Two
Forth River Basin	Allan Water, Devon catchment, River Almond and Water of Leith	Four
Clyde		One
Tay River Basin	Tay catchment and Dundee coast	Three
Don		Two
Dee		One
Spey		One

Integrated list using both spatial and stakeholder engagement

The spatial analysis and responses to the stakeholder survey provided two sets of outputs each suggesting a list of proposed priority catchments. The strength of this project lies in its commitment to the bring together both technical mapping analysis and the views of stakeholders to produce a single prioritised list. This integration was done by identifying those catchments that have both locations of risks identified from the survey (blue dots on the maps provided) *and* those that have a higher normalised score from the spatial analysis (areas that are more yellow on the map).

⁶ The Green Infrastructure Strategic Intervention is undertaking work around Glasgow.

<https://www.nature.scot/funding-and-projects/green-infrastructure-strategic-intervention>

The overall list of proposed priority catchments considering both approaches is provided in Table 1.

Some catchments have only one identified risk each in the survey responses. These risks are all linked to coastal erosion and river flooding or impacts on water temperature and quality. Whilst there is a certain amount of overlap in the two lists, there are catchments identified by only one methodology that could still be considered a priority for other reasons. This detail is captured in the table below.

It is worth noting that the overall evaluation of risk will depend on whether specific risks are considered as individual, combination (multiple) or as cascading impacts. Some organisations have considered each risk in isolation; others have done so by considering multiple and cascading risks. This prevents an over-arching risk statement, as this would require more detailed data collection and analyses. Further research is required to enable a better understanding of how organisations perceive and assess risks to avoid issues of exposure and vulnerability to climate change.

Other catchments benefiting from restoration

The objectives of the research and spatial analytical methods aimed to capture where restoration will achieve multiple benefits. There are, however, other notable catchments and locations where restoration will lead to benefits for either single benefits such a flood risk reduction, or have previously experienced damage due to extreme weather events. The following are some examples only and have been provided to further stimulate discussion on identifying where restoration is required;

- The Nith catchment (1115km²) could be considered, particularly for reducing flood risk to Dumfries.
 - There are sections of the upper catchment with multiple benefits but overall it has lower normalised scores at lower elevations.
 - Climate projections for the catchment indicate that there is likely to be an increase in the number of days with very heavy rain, particularly in the winter period⁷, though this also applies to many catchments on the west of Scotland.
- Areas with bare and eroding peat are present in the Brorar and Shin catchments, as well as the Lewis and Harris Coastal island catchment, if practical aspects (i.e. access) enables the potential for peatland restoration.
 - Specific locations for a particular benefit include Jura (climate regulation) which has peat that is drained but currently in good condition, hence a targeted ditch blocking campaign over the island would help with maintaining its condition.

It is also important to note that there is a spatially stochastic aspect to the probability of an extreme event, particularly heavy rainfall, occurring in any one location or catchment. This means that whilst restoration may be targeted to as set of prioritised catchments, there is a probability that extremes will still occur elsewhere.

Barriers to using nature restoration in Scotland

While the key informant interviews were limited in their contributions to priority catchments as many infrastructure organisations work nationally and are working internally to calculate their own climate risks and areas for investment, they unearthed many factors that limit the use of nature-

⁷ [Scotland's observed climate trends and future projections](#)

based solutions to address climate risk. The barriers identified build on those highlighted by NatureScot in their case studies for [large scale nature restoration](#) and include:

- A lack of demonstrative examples that restoring nature at scale is a suitable and effective alternative to a solution that has already been defined.
- Difficulties in making the business case and accounting for investments in nature. There is lack of examples of investments in nature restoration being good value for money and a challenge around quantification of benefits.
- Regulators largely focus on economics and are limited in considering the social and environmental perspectives. Current cost benefit analysis does not sufficiently capture social benefits.
- Organisations that should be collaborating in this space have incompatible financial cycles and policy target years which makes the prospects of joint funding challenging.
- Government policies lack coherence and decisions makers operate in silos
- There are broader nature market challenges like the availability of suitable options and a clear understanding of added benefit while the 'do nothing option' or status quo has the tactical advantage of being the default option, despite the risks embedded in it (e.g. designed on the assumption of a stable and predictable climate).
- A lack of technical knowledge and data that demonstrates the success of restoration interventions to provide reassurance to key audiences like engineers, regulators and policy makers.
- There is a lack of skills necessary to integrate spatial mapping to climate risk.
- There is need for behaviour/culture change within organisations where they primarily focussed on 'fixing the problem' within their corridor or related to a specific asset to working in true collaboration and partnership.
- Costs can appear be prohibitive (especially given the wide acceptance of externalised costs and risk), so working with lineside neighbours and stakeholders has to be an imperative.

Of those organisations interviewed, there was consensus that current efforts do not go far or fast enough because efforts for restoration are not happening at the right scale – they are too fragmented and piecemeal.

There is a need for national policy alignment and spatial coordination to focus direction, new governance structures and greater collaboration from SEPA, Scottish Government, NatureScot and local authorities.

This could be achieved through existing mechanisms such as Environment and Economy Leaders Group, [regional adaptation partnerships](#), which the Scottish Government has committed to expanding to the whole of Scotland by 2029 in SNAP3. Where priority catchments in Table 1 lie within the area of existing regional adaptation partnerships, these have been identified. Partnerships such as Climate Ready Tayside are focusing on landscape-scale nature restoration as a key priority for building resilience to climate change across the region, and can act as catalysts for equitable and effective action if supported by NatureScot.

Ensuring strong policy alignment and coordinated support is vital to deliver the greatest level of co-benefits and support the most climate vulnerable places and communities. There is a need to associate upstream investments in catchments with impacts downstream on neighbourhoods, villages and city centres that were often prioritised in the survey responses.

To address this, a series of questions, such as the following may help tease out benefits, risks and burdens:

- 'How bad could this be?'
- 'How much does that matter?'
- 'What can we do about it?'
- 'Who pays when it all goes wrong?'
- 'Is that fair/ just?'
- 'How can this help us improve our place?'
- 'What other priorities can this address?'
- 'Who do we need to collaborate with?'

Recommended next steps

Given the potential for nature restoration to deliver multiple benefits and considering the need for careful integration of restoration objectives to avoid unwanted outcomes, we recommend the use of more detailed studies assessing opportunities and trade-offs in undertaking nature restoration within each catchment and during the design of delivery projects.

- NatureScot should use the prioritised catchments together in dialogue with other organisations to convene and interpret assets in selected catchments to identify risks, including the costs of inaction, and share approaches to integrating nature-based solutions. The aim should be to build where there is work already happening and provide evidence of success, for example in areas with existing partnerships ([Forth2O](#)) and initiatives (regional adaptation partnerships, land use partnership and landscape scale project partnerships).
- NatureScot and stakeholders should consider prioritising specific benefits as an approach to reduce the proposed 14 catchments, considering technical feasibility, local stakeholder priorities and capacities, and the potential for co-financing from a range of sources, including infrastructure providers.
- Academic research should focus on removing the barriers to delivery, in particular the need to quantify benefits from nature restoration, this should be a core consideration in the Scottish Governments Strategic Research Programme 2027-32.
- There is a need to better estimate the costs of inaction (maintaining the *status quo*) and use as a guide to inform investment in Nature.
 - This includes understanding the evaluation of Nature-based Solutions and Nature Restoration in a spatial context.
- Prioritisation can use other data integration and criteria application methods alongside the WISE2 approach as well as more comprehensive spatial data coverage, including:
 - Landscape zonation for restoration (e.g. [Gimona and Castellazzi 2025](#)).
 - Wider range of climate change indicators (e.g. [The James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation](#)).
 - Understanding of how climate change may impact [Land Capability for Agriculture](#)
 - Integrating restoration with overall [Land Use Transformations](#) objectives.
 - Utilising improving ecosystem condition monitoring and mapping capabilities (e.g. [Updating Peatland Condition Mapping](#))
- Organisations responsible for key infrastructure that underpins society including our transport networks, energy systems and networks of health and social care all have an

established understanding of climate risk (especially extreme events). Many are now in the process of attaching that risk to specific areas, places and people. A number of major infrastructure providers including Network Rail and Scottish Water will be sharing more relevant geospatial datasets of climate risk in the near future. These can be used to inform ongoing discussions on priority landscapes.

- There needs to be a central record of places that have been flooded.
- There is potential in collaboration with the Climate Ready Infrastructure Forum for a next stage to support the development of an integrated infrastructure map, aligned with locations of shared climate hazards and opportunities for collaborative nature restoration initiatives to deliver adaptation outcomes.
- Crowd sourced and citizen perspectives should be included in further mapping of climate risks. An example of this is the [Climate Ready Southeast Scotland Storymap](#):
- Outputs from the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme (2022-2027) will be of value to inform further analysis and decision making. There is an opportunity to directly link SRP place-based research within the priority catchments to ensure the multiple benefits can be better quantified. This will be critical to demonstrating the benefits accrued.
 - The [Gimona and Castellazzi 2025](#) report (see References) is a good example, as it contains a more detailed integration of data and analysis to identify zonation for restoration.
- There is need for improved linkages between developing methods for restoration prioritisation, including costs, with finance mechanisms. There is need to better estimate the costs / benefits relationship of restoration, including the avoided spend arising from it and the risks embedded in the status quo/ do nothing option.
- Long term maintenance and finance of nature restoration schemes to ensure effectiveness is currently overlooked and is key to their success, hence access to finance is an important factor.
- A Fellowship, funded by the Centres of Expertise, possibly through SEFARI Gateway in 2025-26 is one option to take this work forward.

How the spatial analysis could be further developed.

From a spatial analysis perspective:

- There is scope for a wider range of spatial analysis using more data sets, however for this to work equitably (i.e. using the WISE2 approach) they would need to be at a national level.
- There is scope to better use details available from SEPA on Potential Vulnerable Areas and the Flood Risk Management Strategy to identify specific sub-catchments where nature restoration may reduce river flood risks.
 - Surface water flooding risk may be reduced through integrated nature restoration in urban environments.
- There is potential to use stakeholder engagement to weight specific criteria based on importance of benefits (currently WISE2 uses equal weighting).
- The spatial granularity of the standardised data sets enables more detailed assessments which could be used to help identify more sub-catchments.
- The research identified infrastructure maps; however, these are in different forms and with some omissions on publicly available data (i.e. for security reasons) which presents

challenges for integration during the timescales of this project. For this reason, only the number of buildings has been used in the analysis. Relating buildings to risks, i.e. flooding is a key next step.

Conclusions

The ability of nature restoration to contribute to climate change mitigation through climate regulation, whilst reducing the risks of impacts is dependent on the ecosystem condition and types of nature restoration project developed. Whilst the analysis presented is a robust, data-led approach to identify priority locations, engagement with stakeholders in each area is essential to design a programme of works that will deliver on the aims of this research.

From the analyses we conclude that the proposed catchments are priorities for nature restoration to achieve adaptation outcomes and multiple other objectives. This initial analysis only takes us to a certain point and should be followed with further engagement that might change the prioritisation of the catchments – such as technical feasibility, financing opportunities, and the priorities of local communities.

Further analysis to explore the specific climate risks and adaptation opportunities in each location will be essential to inform the design of solutions in each catchment. This could be aligned to existing work being undertaken by regional adaptation partnerships and regional land use partnerships in Scotland (see maps in SM Figs 37 and 38). It may also be beneficial to align priorities with areas identified as part of the Nature Networks being implemented by local authorities, and where co-investment from infrastructure providers may be possible.

There are many other nature restoration projects being considered, under development or are in early stages of implementation which are not captured in the survey but are being mapped and prioritised by NatureScot separately.

Urgency and timescales

There is considerable urgency in the need to increase momentum in undertaking nature restoration, as there is increasing evidence that the climate is destabilising faster than previously thought, evidenced by record ocean temperatures, increasing cryosphere loss particularly in Antarctica, and increases in extreme events. Mitigation of climate change through reduction in fossil fuel use is not yet occurring, with current National Declared Contributions (as required in the Paris Agreement) globally only reducing emissions to 2.6% from the 2019 levels, whereas this needs to be 43% by 2030 to keep below 1.5°C. By 2035, global emissions need to be cut by 60% compared to 2019 levels. Globally, natural sequestration of CO₂ is declining, which will accelerate climate change (Curran and Curran 2025). This implies the urgency and imperative to work with nature to ensure the delivery of ecosystem services, particularly climate regulation.

Taking an ecosystem-based mitigation and adaptation approach using the restoration of natural ecosystems that have been degraded is increasingly seen as necessary to achieve multiple socio-ecological system benefits including climate mitigation (Munang et al 2013). Healthy ecosystems impart resilience through their better buffering capacity against extremes. However, ecosystem restoration may take time to develop, finance and implement. Some restoration efforts, such as peatland re-wetting using leaky dams may produce positive early benefits, whereas others such as riparian or other forms of woodland creation may take many years before benefits are realised.

Hence the sooner restoration commences, the better the chance of success and conversely, the longer the delay the greater the chance of failure both for net zero and exposure to climate risks.

Considering the urgency of the climate and biodiversity crises the project team recognised that, whilst not a comprehensive approach to restoration priority assessment, we needed to start somewhere and soon to identify proposed prioritised to inform wider discussions. There is urgency to our actions and necessity for stakeholders to be working collaboratively at pace and at scale (Zamurieva et al, 2023).

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